

Tutorial Series on Java Framework for Evolutionary Computation and Decision Making

Tutorial 10: Evolutionary Rejection Sampling

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Abstract

This tutorial introduces a novel method for preference disaggregation: Evolutionary Rejection Sampling.

Keywords: JECDM, preference learning, evolutionary computation, rejection sampling

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1. Introduction

This tutorial should be considered as a supplement to the publication on “Efficient preference learning algorithm for interactive evolutionary multi-objective optimization” [?] (TODO: preprint submitted for revision), where a novel preference disaggregation method named Evolutionary Rejection Sampling (ERS) is presented. Note that ERS per se is not discussed in detail in this tutorial document. For such, the Reader is referred to the cited article. Instead, this tutorial addresses the following:

1. It showcases how to instantiate ERS and use it within the IEMO/D algorithm (Section 2).
2. It overviews the source codes developed for the project realized in [1] (Section 3).

2. On using the Evolutionary Rejection Sampling method

Source package:
`t1_t10.t10_evolutionary_rejection_sampling`

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ERS can be viewed as an evolutionary extension of the Fast Rejection Sampling (FRS) algorithm, which was already introduced in “*Tutorial 4: Decision Support module*” document. The major difference between these two is that ERS samples models via an evolutionary process instead of sampling them randomly, as done in FRS. The evolution is designed to create a set of compatible and uniformly spread models. Conversely, FRS does not account for the uniform distribution of constructed models, and it poorly scales with problem size due to employing unconstrained sampling. Naturally, the better overall performance of ERS is obtained at the cost of the higher computational complexity associated with constructing a single sample.

This tutorial’s source code considers a straightforward use-case example:

- A 3-objective DTLZ2 test problem is tackled.
- IEMO/D coupled with ERS is used for the simulation.
- The simulation is run for 1000 generations.
- The interactions with the Decision-Maker (DM) are triggered in generations: 300, 400, 500, 600, 700.
- The DM’s policy is simulated using an L^∞ -norm with equal weights.
- The feedback is provided through pairwise comparisons of solutions randomly picked from current populations.
- The preference learning is done under the assumption that the DM’s preferences can be modeled using L^∞ -norms.
- The simulation process is visualized using a 3D scatter plot.

Apart from the ERS, the source code introduces nothing new compared to previous tutorials. Thus, it is not examined here in detail (it is accompanied by informative comments, though). For the Reader’s convenience, Listing 1 showcases a code snippet where the ERS is instantiated. The code is relatively straightforward, and the supplied comments should be considered its description (remainder: ERS is developed as

an implementation of the *IConstructor<T>* interface for constructing preference model instances).

Listing 1: Instantiating ERS

```

// Instantiating ERS -----
// Create params container (LNormGenerator
// is responsible for sampling initial
// random models):
ERS.Params<LNorm> pERS = new ERS.Params<>(
    new LNormGenerator(3, Double.
        POSITIVE_INFINITY), 3);
5 pERS._feasibleSamplesToGenerate =
    populationSize; // Population size = no.
    // feasible samples to generate
// Cannot go below the population size (if
// the no. compatible samples generated by
// ERS is smaller, inconsistency is
// triggered):
pERS._inconsistencyThreshold =
    populationSize - 1;
// Use constant no. iterations, i.e.,
// improvement attempts (20000).
// This implementation, however, returns 0
// if preference learning is triggered when
// there is no feedback
10 // (e.g., as a reaction to update in known
// objective space bounds):
pERS._improvementAttemptsLimit = new
    ConstantZeroWhenNoFeedback(20000);
// Limits data on k-nearest neighbors (k is
// limited to 3):
15 pERS._kMostSimilarNeighbors = 3;

// Use the following evolutionary model
// constructor:
// - create models with alpha = Infinity (
// Chebyshev functions)
// - use a tournament selection of size = 2
// - use OnSimplexCombination crossover
// operator with std = 0.2
// - use OnSimplexMutation operator with
// std = 0.2
20 pERS._EMC = new
    EvolutionaryModelConstructor<>(new
    LNormOnSimplex(Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY,
    0.2d, 0.2d), new Tournament<>(2));

// Comparator used: maximizes distance at
// 1-nn, in the case of a tie, checks 2-nn,
// and so on, until the tie is resolved.
pERS._comparator = new
    MostSimilarWithTieResolving<>();

25 // Quantifies similarity between generated
// L-norms (Euclidean distance between
// their weight vectors):
pERS._similarity = new model.similarity.
    lnorm.Euclidean();
// Use default compatibility analyzer:
pERS._compatibilityAnalyzer = new
    CompatibilityAnalyzer();
// Validate consistency of the already
// contained samples instead of starting
// from scratch in each sampling call:
pERS._validateAlreadyExistingSamplesFirst =
    true;

// Optionally the goals initially used in
// IEMO/D can serve as initial compatible
// models for ERS
LNorm [] initialModels = new LNorm[goals.
    length];
// Copy paste params (implementation-
// dependent):
for (int i = 0; i < goals.length; i++)
    initialModels[i] = new LNorm(goals[i].
        getParams()[0].clone(), goals[i].
        getParams()[1][0], null);
pERS._initialModels = initialModels

// Create the ERS method:
ERS<LNorm> ers = new ERS<>(pERS);

// IMPORTANT NOTE: Most of the above fields
// are already set this way by default (
// check the code).
// Another way of instantiating ERS (
// equivalent):
// ers = ERSFactory.getDefaultForLNorms(
//     populationSize, new Constant(20000), 3,
//     Double.POSITIVE_INFINITY,
//     null, new LNormOnSimplex(Double.
//     POSITIVE_INFINITY, 0.2d, 0.2d), 2,
//     initialModels);

```

The source code executes a simulation that is being visualized during the whole process. The expected final render is depicted in Figure 1 for convenience. As expected, IEMO/D was able to suitably learn the DM’s preferences and accordingly narrow the search around the central parts of DTLZ2’s Pareto front. However, unlike FRS, ERS generates uniformly distributed compatible model samples, which may lead to better overall distribution of the constructed population. Indeed, Figure 2 portrays the population (zoomed) using a perspective that reveals a satisfactory distribution of constructed solutions. Note that constraining weighted Chebyshev functions may lead to concave boundaries of compatible weight vectors, which happened in this example.

3. On the “Efficient preference learning algorithm for interactive evolutionary multi-objective optimization” project

Source package: *(Projects) y2025.ERS*

Important note: The article on that project is currently being revised. Until published, the project’s structurization may change.

Figure 1: Expected final visualization product (zoomed out)

Figure 2: Expected final visualization product (zoomed in)

Sources associated with different experiments conducted in [?] are listed in what follows. The codes are not discussed per se, as a reader that is already well-acquainted with the framework and is at least a moderately skilled programmer should find there relatively nothing new nor difficult to comprehend.

1. *common* package: Provides some common classes, e.g., implemented performance indicators or iterable represen-

tations of samplers viewed as implementations of an evolutionary algorithm (for testing using the Experimental module; *EAWrapperIterableSampler* class).

2. *e1_auxiliary*: This package delivers some auxiliary scripts. Specifically:
 - (a) *AnimationERS* and *AnimationFRS*: Perform simulations that were foundations for preparing the animations for [?].
 - (b) *GeneratePCsData*: Generates data on the reference pairs of solutions and artificial Decision Makers. The data is stored in the *pcs.txt* file.
 - (c) *GenerateConceptPlots*: This script generates the conceptual plots portraying the IEMO/D algorithm, which were included in the paper.
 - (d) *OffspringDistribution*: This script examines the performance of the developed reproduction operators. As a final product, it generates a 3D distribution plot portraying the potential outcomes of the reproduction process.
 - (e) *PCsPlot2D* and *PCsPlot3D*: These scripts generate example plots portraying the reference pairs to be compared by the DM, using the data in the *pcs.txt* file.
3. *e2_ers_calibration* package: This package delivers a simple experiment concerning a suitable parameterization of ERS (the standard deviations employed by the reproduction operators). This experiment is considered preliminary, and its results are not presented in the article.
4. *e3_samplers* package: This package delivers the experiment concerning the verification of ERS and FRS when employed as standalone procedures. The core class is *ContainersGetter* that provides suitably parameterized data containers for the *Experimentation* module. The experiment can be executed via the *ExperimentExecutor* class (check configuration before running, e.g., the main path for storing results; note that the experiments are extensive and the calculations can take even days, depending on the hardware specification). The *ExecuteScenarioSummarizer* and *ExecuteCrossSummarizer* summarize the results delivered via *ExperimentExecutor* at the scenario and global (cross-examination) levels. The inner *results* package provides some results already summarized in Excel files and various executables generating plots and Excel tables.
5. *e4_interactive* package: This package delivers the experiment concerning the verification of ERS and FRS when employed as preference learning procedures within the IEMO/D algorithm. The structuration of this package is similar to *e3_samplers*.

References

- [1] Tomczyk, M.K., Kadziński, M., . Efficient preference learning algorithm for interactive evolutionary multi-objective optimization. Preprint doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5279824>.